

BRUCELLA OUTBREAK IN ORGANISED FARM, IMPACT OF ECOLOGY, CLIMATE CHANGE AND MANAGEMENTShashank Vishvakarma¹, Nitin Kumar Bajaj², Pushkar Sharma³, Madhu Shivhare⁴, Pankaj Kumar Umar⁵, Jyoti Dagar⁵, Anand Kumar Yadav⁶, Pushpendra Maravi⁷, Ashutosh Mishra⁸¹Ph.D. Scholar, ⁷M.V.Sc Scholar, Department of Veterinary Gynaecology and Obstetrics, College of Veterinary Science & Animal Husbandry, N.D.V.S.U., Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, 482 001²Associate Professor, ⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Veterinary Gynaecology and Obstetrics, College of Veterinary Science & Animal Husbandry, N.D.V.S.U., Mhow, Madhya Pradesh, 453446³Assistant Professor, Department of Veterinary Gynaecology and Obstetrics, College of Veterinary Science & Animal Husbandry, N.D.V.S.U., Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, 482 001⁵Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Veterinary Pharmacology & Toxicology, College of Veterinary Science & Animal Husbandry, N.D.V.S.U., Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, 482 001⁶Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Animal Reproduction, Gynarcology and Obstetrics., NDRI - National Dairy Research Institute-ICAR, Karnal-132001⁸Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Veterinary Gynaecology and Obstetrics, College of Veterinary Science & Animal Husbandry, DUVASU, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, 281 001

MS Received: 09.08.2024; MS Revised: 20.10.2024; MS Accepted: 21.10.2024

MS 3252

(RESEARCH PAPER IN VETERINARY GYNAECOLOGY AND OBSTETRICS,)

Abstract

Brucellosis, caused by Brucella spp., remains a significant zoonotic and economic concern in India's livestock sector. This paper reviews the outbreak of Brucella in organized farms, exploring its ecological impacts, climate change influences and management strategies. The disease's endemic nature in diverse agro-climatic regions and its socio-economic implications are discussed. Factors contributing to disease spread, such as livestock management practices and environmental conditions, are highlighted. The Bovine Brucellosis Progressive Control Programme (BBPCP) is evaluated as a comprehensive strategy for disease management, emphasizing vaccination, serological testing and farm hygiene practices. Future directions for brucellosis control in India are proposed, underscoring the need for sustained efforts in surveillance, vaccination and public awareness to mitigate the disease's impact on animal health and human livelihoods.

Keywords: Brucellosis, Brucella spp., Zoonotic diseases, Livestock management, Bovine Brucellosis Progressive Control Programme (BBPCP), India

Introduction

Brucellosis, sometimes referred to as "Malta Fever," gets its name from the febrile illness that was prevalent in 19th-century British soldiers stationed in Malta (Aniyappanavar, 2010). India initially recognized brucellosis in 1942 and today the disease is widespread there. Cattle, buffalo, sheep, goats, pigs, dogs and humans have all been shown to be affected by the disease. The most common infectious biotypes are *B. melitensis* biotype-1 in sheep, goats and humans and *B. abortus* biotype-1 in cattle and buffaloes (Verma, 2013). Long-term serological research has revealed that 3% of buffaloes and 5% of cattle are brucellosis-infected (Pothanna, (2018). An agrarian nation like India suffers significant economic losses as a result of brucellosis in animals (Singh *et al.*, 2018). Under various geo- agro-climatic, management, migration and healthcare delivery systems, India maintains a vast and diverse livestock population (Ahlawat and Sharma, 2022). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore. The majority-agrarian character of animal husbandry practices offers plenty of opportunity for species mixing, grazing pastures and composite small livestock holdings, which are kept by over 70% of the rural population.

Zoonotic diseases (ZDs) are a significant cause of illness and death on a global scale. Their increase is related to a number of factors, including climate change, which is linked to a higher risk of transmission of a number of zoonoses because of the effects of elevated temperatures and extreme precipitation events on vectors (Ihekweazu *et al.*, 2021). The pathogenic bacterium *Brucella* spp. can cause large-scale animal epidemics. Additionally, because these pathogens can result in zoonotic illnesses, they endanger the close association between farm households and their livestock, particularly goats (Grace *et al.*, 2012).

The US Centres for Disease Control and Prevention classify *Brucella* spp. as "bioterrorism agents" due to their stability, ability to be aerosolized and potential for large-scale pathogen transmission (Valdes and Valdes, 2022). For up to several days even months, *Brucella* species may survive in milk, urine, water, feces and damp soil. They can also withstand freezing and thawing. The survival of *Brucella* species is enhanced by cooler temperatures (Cordes and Carter, 1979). The majority of developing nations are affected by brucellosis, a livestock reproductive disease that is economically significant (Franc *et al.*, 2018). The condition has zoonotic significance

in underdeveloped nations because it causes infertility, delayed heat, interrupted lactation and loss of calf, wool, meat and milk production (Islam, 2015).

Serological data suggests that brucellosis is extremely endemic in most regions of India (Maiti *et al.*, 1980; Chandramohan *et al.*, 1992; Kalita and Roychaudhury, 1993; Shakya *et al.*, 1995; Isloor *et al.*, 1998a; Chakraborty *et al.*, 2000; Hussain *et al.*, 2000; Mehra *et al.*, 2000 and Chauhan *et al.*, 2000). According to Mehra *et al.* (2000), the seroprevalence rate varied from 6.6% (123/1860) in the central state of Madhya Pradesh to 60% in the northeastern state of Assam. These samples primarily came from sizable herds with a history of infertility and abortion.

It is an unavoidable fact that brucellosis is an important public health issue and that it is endemic in the nation. Consideration of alternative methods for the control and eradication of the disease is necessary due to the potential economic rewards from continued and increased milk production. BBPCP is a village-targeted project that detects infection using pooled milk screening, initiates a 5-year immunization program with *B. abortus* S-19 and screens and eliminates contaminated bulls utilized in sperm production (Renukaradhya *et al.*, 2002).

Outbreak Of Brucella In Farm And Its Impact

The livestock firm may suffer significant financial losses as a result of brucellosis, a significant zoonotic disease that poses a serious risk (Wang *et al.*, 2021 and Peng *et al.*, 2020). The disease is widespread in India and also has the highest populations of cattle and buffaloes and milk production worldwide. Bovine brucellosis, which is caused by *B. abortus*, is still the most common form in animals and is endemic almost everywhere (Corbel, 1997). Due to a lack of resources, policy and knowledge, the prevalence of brucellosis in both humans and animals appears to be rising (Pappas *et al.*, 2006).

Risk Factors

Production methods, agroecological regions, husbandry techniques, interactions with wild animals and management elements are risk factors (Dadar *et al.*, 2021). After reviewing literature from India and other nations, we broadly divide these into four types. Host factor includes age, sex, breed, history of abortions, subsequent breeding and placenta retention.

Management factor includes herd size, single- or mixed-herd, agricultural system, introducing new animals and distance between

farms (Robi and Gelalcha, 2020). Factors affecting farmers include their age, education, training and experience (Kothalawala *et al.*, 2018). Geographical location, climate and the existence of fauna that is susceptible were agroecological factors. Additionally, inadequate floor space has been identified as a risk factor for *Brucella* infection (Coelho *et al.*, 2015).

Other risk factors mentioned include a lack of adequate water, insufficient manure collection and cleaning, poor handling of aborted materials, introduction of new animals from herds with brucellosis or unclear status, herds managed in close confinement and mixed herds. Compared to marginal herds, organized dairy farms are reportedly more likely to have the condition (Kiptanui, 2023).

The disease may be more common in exotic and cross-bred animals than in native cattle, therefore may clarify that organized dairy farms have greater prevalence rates. Exposure to sick animals, physical contact due to close confinement and disease transfer during natural mating and artificial insemination (Minda *et al.*, 2016). Numerous factors contribute to brucellosis in farms, such as lack of knowledge about the disease, a history of reproductive issues in farms and animals (abortion, repeated breeding, retained placentas, vaginal discharge, carpal hygromas and stillbirth) and practices used to prevent brucellosis in farms (vaccination and placenta disposal) (Mitiku and Desa, 2020). On the other hand, a small number of studies found that the prevalence was significantly lower in organized farms than in marginal herds (Shome *et al.*, 2014). These findings may be because of proper management, good sanitation and disinfection, proper placenta disposal, improved animal health awareness and management and vaccination; (Shome *et al.*, 2014). However, the number of these types of farms where studies were conducted was small and not representative of organized farms as a whole.

Although large herds have been observed to be more susceptible to *Brucella* infection, large herds may be kept by farmers with better resources and expertise, which may lead to less disease (Omer *et al.*, 2000). A different study found that medium-sized organized farms had a higher incidence than small- or large-sized farms (Shome *et al.*, 2014). This may be due to the indiscriminate replacement of the herd from an unknown source or to the inferior management and cleanliness practices of medium-sized farms compared to larger farms. Unrestricted trade, routine animal transportation without testing, the use of infected bull semen for artificial insemination and poor farm cleanliness are all factors that may have contributed to the infection's spread. Indiscriminate slaughtering in camels also responsible for higher prevalence (Niranjan *et al.*, 2013).

A high prevalence of diseases is partly a result of the rising demand for foods with animal origins and agricultural intensification (Ducrottoy *et al.*, 2015). Airborne bacterial transmission has been seen in clinical laboratories and butcherries (Shilenge, 2014). Additionally, it can be challenging to contain illness outbreaks if veterinary services are unavailable (Steele *et al.*, 2021).

According to Govindaraj *et al.* (2016), inadequate understanding of brucellosis is highly linked to the disease's prevalence, suggesting a vicious circle between underreporting/under-diagnosis and farmers' lack of awareness (Mahmoodabad *et al.*, 2008). In terms of bovine brucellosis, farmers in the nation had a moderate degree of knowledge, attitudes and practices, but they had very little grasp of the zoonotic aspect of the disease (Ismail *et al.*, 2019). Educating communities about bovine brucellosis and its impact on public health, as well as educating people about the safer consumption of animal-sourced foods, are crucial (Bifo *et al.*, 2020).

Impact Of Ecology

The resurgence and epidemiology of zoonoses are complicated and dynamic, impacted by a variety of variables that can essentially be categorized as human-related, pathogen-related and climate/environment-related; nevertheless, there is a significant interplay between these parameters (Fong and Fong, 2017). Modern lifestyle trends like ecotourism, increased exposure from hunting or pet

ownership and gastronomic practices are examples of human-related factors.

Other human-related factors include significant changes in political regimes, conflict with an accompanying breakdown of public health and surveillance infrastructure, voluntary or involuntary immigration and loosening of border controls. Changes in ecosystems and biodiversity that affect the composition of the local fauna are among the pathogen-related factors, as are pressures for the selection of virulence and resistance, expansion of disease hosts and genetic variability (Ennos, 2015).

Issues relating to the climate and environment, whether they are local or global may affect host–vector life cycles through varying mechanisms (Tabachnick, 2010). The development of predictive models for the impact of environmental projects on infectious disease, awareness of the risk posed to immunocompromised populations, recognition of the chronicity burden for some zoonoses and the development of various evaluations of the overall stress imposed by a zoonotic infection on a household, instead of one individual, are just a few of the newer issues that need to be clarified.

The incidence of zoonoses has been impacted by socioeconomic and political changes in human behavior in a variety of ways. Since the world's population has been steadily growing, there has been an increase in the need for food, particularly meat. As a result of the industrialization of livestock farming and the use of intensive husbandry techniques, huge animal reservoirs have been developed in which an infection can spread from one animal to another and then jump species (a pathway that was theoretically implicated in the genesis of both SARS and pandemic influenza outbreaks); This also applies to the large, less hygienic livestock markets in the East (Cascio *et al.*, 2011).

Climate Change

Brucella spp. is more likely to survive in cooler environments. A systemic infection, brucellosis can affect any organ or tissue in the body (Davidson and Sykes, 2021). Direct inoculation through skin wounds and abrasions, inoculation through the conjunctival sac of the eyes, inhalation of infectious aerosols and consumption of infectious milk or milk products are common ways to contract an illness (Almashhadany *et al.*, 2022).

Given that Southeast Asia has the lowest milk consumption in the globe, the latter is an unlikely etiology. Animal birth fluids that have been infected are the main source of brucellosis infection in humans. Pathogens can now spread by novel vectors, including insects that are colonizing new areas, as a result of climate change and the globalization of trade and migration. Important bacterial zoonotic infections called *Brucella melitensis* are linked to goats, other livestock and humans (Blasco and Molina-Flores, 2011).

Due to their low infectious dosage, environmental resistance and capacity for airborne dissemination via pathogen aerosolization, these diseases can result in large-scale outbreaks. Additionally, *Brucella* spp. can negatively affect rural livelihoods economically by lowering production as a result of cattle herd reproductive loss. The need for increased livestock production also leads to the expansion of farming in previously non-inhabited areas, through deforestation for farm development or common breeding areas for livestock and wildlife species carrying a disease (Cascio *et al.*, 2011).

Through the widespread, frequently uncontrolled use of antibiotics in veterinary medicine and the non-selective, non-rotational use of pesticides (in the case of zoonotic vectors), environmental or human pressure can be exerted on the selection of strains that are more virulent or resistant to available treatments (a characteristic that is also known for species jumping and is therefore favored by pathogen biodiversity). Human intrusion into any ecosystem is disruptive and the resulting disequilibrium may create a conservatory for zoonotic agents (Cascio *et al.*, 2011).

Management And Control Programme

Managing animal sickness and food cleanliness are typically done in tandem with decreasing human occurrence. *Brucella* spp. is

successfully eliminated by pasteurization, hence thoroughly boiling meat is advised. Although it can be challenging to change cultural habits, it is not advisable to consume raw milk, meat or placentas (Thendji, 2023). Before other animals, such as farm dogs and cats and kids, can be exposed to parturition materials, especially aborted fetuses and placenta - it is best to remove and burn them to limit transmission across a herd (Plummer *et al.*, 2018). Daily, waste is cleaned up. In a herd, regular disinfection performed more than three times annually lowers incidence.

Herds that are free of *Brucella* should only be utilised to purchase replacement livestock (Mai *et al.*, 2012). Thanks to programmes and vaccinations that are available for both *B. abortus* and *B. melitensis* in livestock, *Brucella spp.* have been successfully removed from areas. However, there are currently no vaccines that are 100 percent effective. Only when all other preventative measures have failed are vaccination approaches advised.

For the prevention of caprine and ovine brucellosis, the Rev. 1 *B. melitensis* vaccine is made from strains of dead bacteria (Banai, 2002). Because it requires both a political and financial commitment from the government as well as remuneration to farmers, implementing test and cull procedures is challenging. According to the World Organization for Animal Health (WOAH, formerly OIE), animals shouldn't be given antibiotics (Lourens, 2023).

Serological Examination

Serological techniques, such as the Rose Bengal plate agglutination test (RBPT) and the indirect enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (iELISA), are used to check all of the sera samples for brucellosis.

Serological tests are cost-effective and reliable diagnostic tools due to the strong correlation between *Brucella* isolation and positive results in both serum and milk tests. When assessing tests for *B. abortus* antibodies in milk and serum, serological tests are the primary methods for detecting infected herds and diagnosing brucellosis in individual animals (Noriello, 2004). The Rose Bengal plate test (RBPT) is the most commonly used screening test for brucellosis in both humans and animals because of its simplicity and ease of reading, though the results can be influenced by the examiner's experience (Cho *et al.*, 2010). Due to the occurrence of false positives and negatives in MRT and RBPT, recent studies have highlighted the use of Enzyme-linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) for detecting *B. abortus* antibodies in bovine milk or serum (Hunter and Allen, 1972; McGiven *et al.*, 2003 and Patel, 2007). The indirect ELISA is highly sensitive and specific, capable of processing large numbers of samples quickly and economically, with sensitivity and specificity ranging from 98 to 99% for both serum and milk ELISA (Vanzini *et al.*, 1998). ELISA has been found to be a superior serological test compared to RBPT and is recommended for animal screening (Ghodasora *et al.*, 2010). The milk-ELISA for brucellosis is an effective alternative to serum-ELISA and is more sensitive than MRT (Bertu *et al.*, 2010).

Rose Bengal Plate Agglutination Test (RBPT)

The Rose Bengal Plate Test (RBPT), also known as the card test or buffered *Brucella* antigen test, is a spot agglutination technique (Stemshorn *et al.*, 1985). It employs a suspension of *B. abortus* smooth cells stained with Rose Bengal dye, buffered to a pH of 3.65. At a neutral pH, this test can detect the presence of IgM, IgG1, and IgG2, though IgM is typically the most active. However, at the buffered pH of 3.65, RBPT prevents agglutination with IgM and primarily measures IgG1 (Corbel, 1972). While the test yields few false negatives, it may produce numerous false positives, often due to reactions with IgM in previously vaccinated animals. In regions where vaccination is not common, this test effectively records animal exposure to *Brucella* organisms.

Internationally, RBPT is recommended for screening brucellosis in small ruminants, although the antigen lacks standardization (Kaltungo *et al.*, 2014). The low pH of the antigen increases the test's specificity, while the temperature of the antigen and the surrounding environment can affect both the sensitivity and specificity of the test (Macmillan *et al.*, 1990). Corbel (1972) noted that the test's sensitivity is linked to

fractions containing immunoglobulin IgG, especially IgG1. The Indian Veterinary Research Institute I.V.R.I., Izatnagar, Uttar Pradesh, provided the colored antigen for the RBPT and the test was carried out by the manufacturer's instructions. On a flat glass plate, an equal volume of antigen and serum were combined and distributed. When there was no agglutination or there was, the results in RBPT were deemed negative or positive, respectively.

Indirect Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (iELISA)

The IDEXX Brucellosis antibody test kit (IDEXX, Montpellier, France), which enables the examination of individual sera samples, carried out the iELISA. Indirect ELISA was standardized by the checkerboard titration method as described by Wright *et al.* (1993). *Brucella* LPS antigen was diluted in carbonate coating buffer to a concentration as determined by checkerboard titration, i.e. 1.25 µg/ml. For coating, 100 µl of diluted antigen was added to each well of flat bottom microtitration plates (Titertek, Flow Laboratories, Catalog No. 76-204-05) and incubated for 18 h at 4°C. The plates were washed five times with phosphate buffer saline tween-20 (PBST). All the sera were diluted 1:50 in PBST and 100 µl of the diluted sera was dispensed in each well of the micro-titration plate and incubated for one hour at 37°C. After another washing cycle with PBST, 10 µl of diluted rabbit anti-bovine IgG whole molecule conjugated to horseradish peroxidase (Cappel, USA) diluted 1:1000 was added to all the wells of micro-titration plate followed by another 60 min of incubation at 37°C. After the washing cycle, 100 µl of substrate (2,2'-azino diethyl benzothiazoline sulfonic acid / ABTS) solution was added into each well of ELISA plate and incubated with shaking for 15 min at 37°C. The reaction was stopped by the addition of 100 µl of 4% SDS solution. Development of colour was assessed by a spectrophotometer (BDSL, Immunoskan MS) at 405 nm. Standard positive and negative serum controls were also included in each plate (Munir *et al.*, 2008).

Control Strategy

The control strategy at dairy farms was executed by employing the following steps:

Testing and Segregation of Positive Animals

All animals older than 4 months had their serum analysed by RBPT and iELISA for the presence of *B. abortus* antibodies and those that were positive need to be separated.

Decontamination of Farm Premises

With a 1% solution of phenol, the calving pens were cleaned and disinfected. With the aid of a 1% phenol solution, the housing shed and milking area was also cleaned and sanitised (Radositis *et al.*, 2007).

Vaccination of Animals

It was advised that dairy farm owners test their animals and vaccinate all female cows who were seronegative above the age of four months with the S19 vaccine. Due to the risk of orchitis as a side effect, immunization is not advised for males (Olsen and Palmer, 2014). Calves older than four months were given a 1/20th dose of the usual dose of the S19 vaccine.

The traditional method of immunization, testing, quarantine and slaughter with compensation schemes is less successful or practical in low- and middle-income countries (Bagheri Nejad *et al.*, 2020). More specific control strategies might be more beneficial. The most effective preventative method may be vaccination, as eradication may be prohibitively expensive. Due to the significant financial loss to the struggling farmers, testing and slaughtering is not a simple solution. Cattle slaughter is prohibited in India due to socio-religious reasons, making it much more challenging. In several regions of India, the killing of cattle is officially prohibited (Sharma, 2019).

Periodic testing of all animals and segregation of seropositive animals (test and segregation approach) in a separate facility from the main farm was reported to lower the number of seropositive animals from 12.4% to 1.2% in Uttar Pradesh (Sharma *et al.*, 2023). This, together with improved housing, hygienic disposal of abortion materials and vaccination of calves during pregnancy, may aid in lowering the prevalence of brucellosis. Another study conducted in Punjab discovered that the *B. abortus* S19 vaccination decreased the rate of

abortion in cows from 8% to 1% and in buffalo from 3% to 1%. The creation of a live vaccination devoid of smooth lipopolysaccharide (SLPS), which can help distinguish infected from vaccinated animals and so eliminate unnecessary further testing and animal slaughter, has helped to partially solve the problem of positive reactions in serological screens. It has been suggested that RB51 be used in India after being effectively utilized in the USA since 1996 to prevent and eradicate bovine brucellosis. OIE advises vaccination against *Brucella* S19 and RB51, but vaccination effectiveness may be compromised in cases of severe exposure (Saxena, 2021).

In low- and middle-income countries, where vaccines may need to be more thermostable and longer-lasting to reduce the burden of immunizing dairy animals too frequently, these factors are frequently lacking. Efficient vaccination benefits from improved livestock management systems, good access to veterinary services, adequate supply of vaccines and constant refrigeration. Therefore, efforts must be undertaken to create more potent vaccines that are best suited for use in low-income countries (Nuvey *et al.*, 2022).

Control and eradication program

BBPCP or the Bovine Brucellosis Progressive Control Programme, is a novel strategy. The village treated scheme included checking pooled milk for infection, starting a 5-year vaccination program with *B. abortus* S-19 and screening and culling infected bulls used to produce semen (Renukaradhya *et al.*, 2002).

One such practical strategy is BBPCP, which was developed by the Project Directorate on ADMAS based on the key characteristics listed below. Since the BBPCP cannot identify specific afflicted animals, distress sales are no longer possible. The village is recognized by BBPCP as a herd for control and confinement and this includes rural milk cooperatives at every step of the vaccination-based diagnostic and control process (Renukaradhya *et al.*, 2002).

Milk cooperatives are willing to cover the cost of calf hood vaccinations and ELISA milk testing (Refai, 2002). BBPCP is a time-bound, rigorous, location-focused control plan that lasts for five years. Immunization against *B. abortus* S-19 for all female calves aged 6 to 8 months in affected villages. Milk ELISA is used to identify non-infected communities twice a year for indication of new infection. Post-vaccination seroconversion survey to confirm the success of vaccination. Less than Rs. 10 (US\$ 0.2) must be paid by the milk cooperatives for each calf to receive a vaccination. The BBPCP method is straightforward, workable and successful. BBPCP supports the creation of recognized herds and settlements. Bovine infection in humans is drastically decreased.

To be considered: a national commission for the eradication of brucellosis. The *B. abortus* S-19 immunization in infected villages (5-year program), the mass screening and castration of infected bulls and the biennial village-level screening of pooled milk samples are the three main components of BBPCP (Renukaradhya *et al.*, 2002).

Laboratory network for implementation of BBPCP

At the state, regional and national levels, India has well-developed laboratory investigative facilities. The diagnostic laboratory at the state level typically consists of a central referral facility for diagnostic testing and auxiliary, constrained laboratory facilities at the district level. Additionally, diagnostic services are offered by the veterinary colleges and institutions of the Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR). At the headquarters of each state, a national network of 32 ELISA labs has been established as part of the strengthening of veterinary services. All of these resources are usable for BBPCP (Renukaradhya *et al.*, 2002).

Future strategies for brucellosis management/eradication in India. Bovine brucellosis prevention initiatives are gaining momentum as more people become aware of the financial benefits of the dairy industry's fast growth (Sheehy *et al.*, 1996). The cost of an abortion is estimated to be Rs. 5000 (US\$ 100) for the farmer, which can simply be avoided by implementing control measures.

The additional benefit of lowering infertility retained memories, metritis and production losses makes vaccinating newborns an

appealing idea. Additionally, veterinarians are more aware of the risk of contracting brucellosis from infected herds, which has led them to endorse milk-based brucellosis testing and vaccination programs (Wapenaar *et al.*, 2017). Due to the ban on cow slaughter, the country's options for brucellosis control are limited. Additionally, there is an increased emphasis on quarantining and isolating all affected animals until they die to stop the spread of illness (Fèvre *et al.*, 2006).

The expense of maintaining such diseased and unproductive animals is astronomical and unprofitable. Alternative strategies are needed in this situation to prevent the spread of infection through animal movement and boosted herd immunity through vaccination and zoo sanitation. The idea of BBPCP seems to be a practical strategy for gradual control that will eventually result in the disease's eradication. There has been a promising start and the program is receiving a ton of interest (Renukaradhya *et al.*, 2002).

There is evidence of cross-infection whenever there is a high ratio between these two host populations. The extent of the infection in sheep and goats is not well understood and any epidemiological analysis needs to take brucellosis in ruminants into full consideration. Additionally, no vaccination is currently offered in the nation for use with sheep and goats. Sheep, goats and pigs can all be subjected to a test and slaughter regulation (Shirima, 2005).

Result and Discussion:

Brucellosis, caused by *Brucella* spp., remains prevalent in India's livestock, affecting cattle, buffaloes, sheep, goats and humans. The disease causes significant economic losses due to reproductive issues such as abortion, infertility and reduced milk production (Mantur and Amarnath, 2008). Factors such as agro-climatic conditions, wildlife interactions and climate change influence the spread of brucellosis. Cooler temperatures facilitate *Brucella* spp. survival, while environmental disturbances and biodiversity changes affect disease dynamics (Arif and Thomson, 2023). However, the Bovine Brucellosis Progressive Control Programme (BBPCP) is crucial for disease management. It includes vaccination (e.g., *B. abortus* S-19), serological testing (RBPT, iELISA) and farm hygiene practices. Education and public awareness are also vital to control zoonotic transmission (Pal *et al.*, 2017).

Also, various factors contribute to brucellosis spread, including herd size, animal movements, inadequate hygiene and lack of farmer awareness. Organized farms generally exhibit better disease control due to improved management practices and vaccination (Abera *et al.*, 2019). Strategies like test-and-segregate, vaccination drives and stringent biosecurity measures have shown effectiveness in reducing brucellosis prevalence. However, challenges remain in implementation due to socio-economic factors and cultural practices (Islam *et al.*, 2020).

Continued surveillance, enhanced vaccination strategies and integration of One Health approaches are crucial for sustained brucellosis control. Developing more effective vaccines and improving diagnostic capabilities are also recommended (Ghanbari *et al.*, 2020). The study underscores the global significance of brucellosis as a zoonotic disease and highlights the need for international collaboration in disease monitoring and control.

Overall, while brucellosis poses significant challenges to India's livestock sector and public health, concerted efforts through targeted control programs and interdisciplinary approaches offer hope for mitigating its impact in the future.

Conclusion

According to long-term serological research, 3% of buffaloes and 5% of cattle are brucellosis-positive.

In an agrarian nation like India, brucellosis in livestock causes significant economic losses.

The nation lacks a well-organized and efficient brucellosis control programme.

The adult hood vaccination technique, together with adoption of suitable hygienic measures and segregation of sero-positive animals,

may therefore be employed if a dairyman wants to control brucellosis on his infected dairy farm in the least amount of time.

The population survey of the disease has been carried out on a wide scale in numerous states due to the domestic development of serum and milk-based ELISA kits and plans for the control of the disease through calf-hood vaccination are being developed.

Bovine Brucellosis Progressive Control Programme (BBPCP) is an innovative strategy that aims to address the fundamental issues of the restriction on cow slaughter, the distress sale of animals after a positive serological diagnosis of brucellosis and the lack of a disease control strategy.

References

1. **Abera, A., Denek, Y. and Tolosa, T. 2019.** Bovine brucellosis: Seroprevalence and its potential risk factors in smallholder dairy farms in Hawassa Town, Southern Ethiopia. *Ethiopian Veterinary Journal*, **23**(2): 41-63.
2. **hAlmashhadany, D.A., Zefenkey, Z.F., Hassannejad, S., Mohammed, N.J., Rashid, R.F., Hassan, R.R. and Hassan, A.O. 2022.** Milk Borne Brucellosis. In *Current Issues and Advances in the Dairy Industry*. IntechOpen.
3. **Aniyappanavar, D. 2010.** *Serological Study of Brucella Infections in the High-Risk Population and in Patients with Fever in and Around Kolar* (Doctoral dissertation, Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences (India)).
4. **Arif, S. and Thomson. 2023.** Bovine brucellosis in pakistan: epidemiological investigations of a zoonotic disease. *Zoonosis, Unique Scientific Publishers, Faisalabad, Pakistan*, **4**: 420-431.
5. **Banai, M. 2002.** Control of small ruminant brucellosis by use of *Brucella melitensis* Rev. 1 vaccine: laboratory aspects and field observations. *Veterinary Microbiology*, **90**(1-4): 497-519.
6. **Bertu, W.J., Dapar, M., Gusi, A.M., Ngulukun, S.S., Leo, S. and Jwander, L.D. 2010.** Prevalence of brucella antibodies in marketed milk in Jos and environs. *African Journal of Food Science*, **4**(2): 62-64.
7. **Blasco, J.M. and Molina-Flores, B. 2011.** Control and eradication of *Brucella melitensis* infection in sheep and goats. *Veterinary Clinics: Food Animal Practice*, **27**(1): 95-104.
8. **Boral, R., Singh, M. and Singh, D.K. 2009.** Status and strategies for control of brucellosis-a review. *Indian Journal of Animal Sciences*, **79**(12): 1191-1199.
9. **Burns, R.J., Siengsanun-Lamont, J. and Blacksell, S.D. 2023.** A review of coxiellosis (Q fever) and brucellosis in goats and humans: Implications for disease control in smallholder farming systems in Southeast Asia. *One Health*, 100568.
10. **Cascio, A., Bosilkovski, M., Rodriguez-Morales, A.J. and Pappas, G. 2011.** The socio-ecology of zoonotic infections. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection*, **17**(3): 336-342.
11. **Cho, D., Nam, H., Kim, J., Heo, E., Cho, Y., Hwang, I., Kim, J., Kim, J. and Jung, S. 2010.** Quantative Rose Bengal Test for diagnosis of bovine brucellosis. *J. Immunoassay Immunochem.*, **31**(2): 120-30.
12. **Coelho, A. C., Diez, J. G., & Coelho, A. M. 2015.** Risk factors for *Brucella* spp. in domestic and wild animals. In *Updates on Brucellosis*, pp. 1-31.
13. **Corbel, M.J. 1972.** Characterisation of antibodies active in the Rose Bengal plate test. *Vet. Rec.* **9**: 484-485. **Cordes, D.O. and Carter, M.E. 1979.** Persistence of *Brucella abortus* infection in six herds of cattle under brucellosis eradication. *New Zealand Veterinary Journal*, **27**(12): 255-259.
14. **Dadar, M., Tiwari, R., Sharun, K. and Dhama, K. 2021.** Importance of brucellosis control programs of livestock on the improvement of one health. *Veterinary Quarterly*, **41**(1): 137-151.
15. **Davidson, A.P. and Sykes, J.E. 2021.** Canine brucellosis. In *Greene's Infectious Diseases of the Dog and Cat* (pp. 876-892). WB Saunders.
16. **Deka, R.P., Magnusson, U., Grace, D. and Lindahl, J. 2018.** Bovine brucellosis: prevalence, risk factors, economic cost and control options with particular reference to India-a review. *Infection Ecology and Epidemiology*, **8**(1): 1556548.
17. **Ducrottoy, M.J., Ammary, K., Ait Lbacha, H., Zouagui, Z., Mick, V., Prevost, L. and Benkirane, A. 2015.** Narrative overview of animal and human brucellosis in Morocco: intensification of livestock production as a driver for emergence? *Infectious Diseases of Poverty*, **4**: 1-21.
18. **El Amri, H., Boukharta, M., Zakhham, F. and Ennaji, M. M. 2020.** Emergence and reemergence of viral zoonotic diseases: concepts and factors of emerging and reemerging globalization of health threats. In *Emerging and reemerging viral pathogens* (pp. 619-634). Academic Press.
19. **Ennos, R.A. 2015.** Resilience of forests to pathogens: an evolutionary ecology perspective. *Forestry: An International Journal of Forest Research*, **88**(1): 41-52.
20. **Fèvre, E.M., Bronsvoort, B.M.D.C., Hamilton, K.A. and Cleaveland, S. 2006.** Animal movements and the spread of infectious diseases. *Trends in Microbiology*, **14**(3): 125-131.
21. **Fong, I.W. and Fong, I.W. 2017.** Animals and mechanisms of disease transmission. *Emerging Zoonoses: A Worldwide Perspective*, **17**(3): 15-38.
22. **Franc, K.A., Krecek, R.C., Häsler, B.N. and Arenas-Gamboa, A.M. 2018.** Brucellosis remains a neglected disease in the developing world: a call for interdisciplinary action. *BMC Public Health*, **18**: 1-9.
23. **Ghanbari, M.K., Gorji, H.A., Behzadifar, M., Sane, N., Mehedi, N. and Bragazzi, N.L. 2020.** One health approach to tackle brucellosis: a systematic review. *Tropical Medicine and Health*, **48**: 1-10.
24. **Ghodasara, S.N., Roy, A. and Bhandari, B.B. 2010.** Comparison of Rose Bengal plate agglutination, standard tube agglutination and indirect ELISA tests for detection of *Brucella* antibodies in cows and buffaloes. *Veterinary World*, **3**(2): 61.
25. **Govindasamy, K. 2020.** *A One Health systems approach to the epidemiology, management and regulatory control of bovine brucellosis at the human-cattle-farm interface in Gauteng, South Africa* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Pretoria).
26. **Grace, D., Mutua, F.K., Ochungo, P., Kruska, R.L., Jones, K., Brierley, L. and Ogutu, F. 2012.** Mapping of poverty and likely zoonoses hotspots.
27. **Hunter, D. and Allen, J. 1972.** An evaluation of milk and blood tests used to diagnose brucellosis. *Vet. Rec.*, **1**(13):310-312.
28. **Ihekweazu, C., Michael, C.A., Nguku, P.M., Waziri, N.E., Habib, A. G., Muturi, M. and Gloria, O. 2021.** Prioritization of zoonotic diseases of public health significance in Nigeria using the one-health approach. *One Health*, **13**: 100257.
29. **Islam, M.H. 2015.** *Epidemiological Investigation of Brucellosis, Toxoplasmosis and Coxiellosis Associated with Reproductive Disorders in Small Ruminants* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Rajshahi).
30. **Islam, S.S., Rumi, T.B., Kabir, S.L., van der Zanden, A.G., Kapur, V., Rahman, A.A. and Rahim, Z. 2020.** Bovine tuberculosis prevalence and risk factors in selected districts of Bangladesh. *PloS One*, **15**(11): e0241717.

31. **Kaltungo, B.Y., Saidu, S.N.A., Sackey, A.K.B. and Kazeem, H.M. 2014.** A review on diagnostic techniques for brucellosis. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, **13**(1): 1-10.
32. **Kaltungo, B.Y., Saidu, S.N.A., Sackey, A.K.B. and Kazeem, H.M. 2014.** A review on diagnostic techniques for brucellosis. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, **13**(1): 1-10.
33. **Kiptanui, J. 2023.** *Seroprevalence Estimates of Brucellosis and Coxiellosis in Cattle, Sheep and Goats: Associated Risk Factors and Perception in Livestock Farmers in Nandi County, Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Nairobi).
34. **Lourens, C.W. 2023.** *Development of a real time PCR assay to distinguish between Coxiella burnetii and Coxiella-like endosymbionts* (Doctoral dissertation, North-West University (South Africa)).
35. **MacMillan, A.P., Greiser-Wilke, I., Moennig, V. and Mathias, L. A. (1990).** A competition enzyme immunoassay for brucellosis diagnosis. *DTW. DeutscheTierärztliche Wochenschrift*, **97**(2): 83-85.
36. **Mai, H.M., Irons, P.C., Kabir, J. and Thompson, P.N. 2012.** A large seroprevalence survey of brucellosis in cattle herds under diverse production systems in northern Nigeria. *BMC Veterinary Research*, **8**: 1-14.
37. **Makwavarara, T. (2018).** *Use of a modified Hazard analysis and critical control points (HACCP) approach for the evaluation of bovine brucellosis control programmes* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Pretoria).
38. **Mantur, B.G. and Amarnath, S.K. 2008.** Brucellosis in India—a review. *Journal of biosciences*, **33**(4): 539-547.
39. **McGiven, J.A., Tucker, J.D., Perrett, L.L., Stack, J.A., Brew, S.D. and MacMillan, A.P. 2003.** Validation of FPA and cELISA for the detection of antibodies to *Brucella abortus* in cattle sera and comparison to SAT, CFT, and iELISA. *Journal of Immunological Methods*, **278**(1-2): 171-178.
40. **Mitiku, W. and Desa, G. 2020.** Review of bovine brucellosis and its public health significance. *Healthcare Review*, **1**(2): 16-33.
41. **Munir, R., Rehman, S.T., Kausar, R., Naqvi, S.M. and Farooq, U. 2008.** Indirect Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay for diagnosis of brucellosis in buffaloes. *Acta Veterinaria Brno*, **77**(3): 401-406.
42. **Naazir, S., Naazir, N., Naazir, T., Yousaf, A., Wakeel, A., Noori, B. and Habib, F. 2021.** Incidences of brucella abortus in serum and milk samples of cattle in rawalpindi. *Research in: Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences*, **5**(3).
43. **Niranjan, S.K., Ganguly, I., Behl, R. and Pundir, R. K. 2013.** Camel Genetic Resources of India. *Sustainable Utilization of Indigenous Animal Genetic Resources of India*, 96-100.
44. **Noriello S. 2004.** Laboratory-acquired brucellosis- Detection of *Brucella abortus* in Bovine Milk by Polymerase Chain Reaction. *Emerg. Infect. Dis.*, **10**: 1848-1850.
45. **Nuvey, F.S., Arkoazi, J., Hattendorf, J., Mensah, G. I., Addo, K. K., Fink, G. and Bonfoh, B. 2022.** Effectiveness and profitability of preventive veterinary interventions in controlling infectious diseases of ruminant livestock in sub-Saharan Africa: a scoping review. *BMC Veterinary Research*, **18**(1): 332.
46. **Omer, M.K., Skjerve, E., Woldehiwet, Z. and Holstad, G. 2000.** Risk factors for *Brucella* spp. infection in dairy cattle farms in Asmara, State of Eritrea. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, **46**(4): 257-265.
47. **Pal, M., Gizaw, F., Fekadu, G., Alemayehu, G. Kandi, V. 2017.** Public health and economic importance of bovine Brucellosis: an overview. *Am J Epidemiol*, **5**(2): 27-34.
48. **Patel, T. 2007.** *Serological, cultural and molecular detection of Brucella infection in bovine including quantification in milk by real time PCR* (Doctoral dissertation).
49. **Pathak, A.D. 2015.** *Epidemiology of Brucellosis Among Humans and Animals in Goa Region* (Doctoral dissertation, Goa University).
50. **Plummer, P.J., McClure, J.T., Menzies, P., Morley, P.S., Van den Brom, R. and Van Metre, D.C. 2018.** Management of *Coxiella burnetii* infection in livestock populations and the associated zoonotic risk: A consensus statement. *Journal of Veterinary Internal Medicine*, **32**(5): 1481-1494.
51. **Pothanna, J. 2018.** Sero epidemiology and molecular diagnosis of brucellosis in cattle and man in selected goshalas of Telangana state.
52. **Pratim Deka, R. 2021.** Epidemiology of *Brucella* infection and cost of reproductive disorders in dairy animals in Assam and Bihar, India.
53. **Refai, M. 2002.** Incidence and control of brucellosis in the Near East region. *Veterinary Microbiology*, **90**(1-4): 81-110.
54. **Renukaradhya, G.J., Isloor, S. and Rajasekhar, M. 2002.** Epidemiology, zoonotic aspects, vaccination and control/eradication of brucellosis in India. *Veterinary microbiology*, **90**(1-4): 183-195.
55. **Robi, D.T. and Gelalcha, B.D. 2020.** Epidemiological investigation of brucellosis in breeding female cattle under the traditional production system of Jimma zone in Ethiopia. *Veterinary and animal science*, **9**: 100117.
56. **Saxena, H.M. 2021.** Brucellosis: The Second Most Important, Yet Neglected, Zoonotic Disease. *World Journal of Veterinary Science*, **9**: 40-49.
57. **Sharma, D., Singathia, R., Rathore, K. and Sain, A. 2021.** Bovine brucellosis outbreaks and their successful management by adulthood vaccination at udaipur region of southern Rajasthan. *Intl. J. Livestock Res*, **11**(5): 11-16.
58. **Sharma, R. 2019.** The 'Cow Protection' discourse in India: The making of a 'movement'. In *Mapping India* Routledge India pp. 133-152.
59. **Sharma, V., Pandey, P., Singh, P. and Parmar, M. 2023.** Host-Pathogen Interactions, Diagnostics, and Control Measures for Brucellosis in Ruminants-A review. *Journal of Animal Research*, **13**(5): 709-718.
60. **Sheehy, D.P., Hamilton, W.T., Kreuter, U.P., Simpson, J.R., Stuth, J.W. and Conner, J.R. 1996.** Interactions between livestock production systems and the environment. *Environmental Impact Assessment of Livestock Production in Grassland and Mixed Rainfed Systems II. Grassland-based Systems in Temperate Zones (LGT). Grazingland Management Systems Inc. Bryan, Texas.*
61. **Shilenge, L. 2014.** *Microbial hazards associated with meat processing in butcherries within Mangaung Metropolitan Municipal area* (Doctoral dissertation, Bloemfontein: Central University of Technology, Free State).
62. **Shirima, G.M. 2005.** *The epidemiology of brucellosis in animals and humans in Arusha and Manyara regions in Tanzania* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Glasgow).
63. **Shome, R., Padmashree, B.S., Krithiga, N., Triveni, K., Sahay, S., Shome, B.R. and Rahman, H. 2014.** Bovine brucellosis in organized farms of India-an assessment of diagnostic assays and risk factors. *Adv Anim Vet Sci*, **2**(10): 557-564.
64. **Singh, B.B., Khatkar, M.S., Aulakh, R.S., Gill, J.P.S. and Dhand, N.K. 2018.** Estimation of the health and economic burden of human brucellosis in India. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, **154**: 148-155.
65. **Steele, S.G., Mor, S.M. and Toribio, J.A.L. 2021.** 'It's our job': Constraints to investigation of atypical disease events—

- Opinions of Australian veterinarians. *Zoonoses and Public Health*, **68**(5): 493-502.
66. **Stemshorn, B.W., Forbes, L.B., Eaglesome, M.D., Nielsen, K.H., Robertson, F.J. and Samagh, B.S. 1985.** A comparison of standard serological tests for the diagnosis of bovine brucellosis in Canada. *Canadian Journal of Comparative Medicine*, **49**(4): 391.
67. **Tabachnick, W.J. 2010.** Challenges in predicting climate and environmental effects on vector-borne disease epizootics in a changing world. *Journal of Experimental Biology*, **213**(6): 946-954.
68. **Thendji, M.L. 2023.** Risk of human exposure to brucella pathogens through consumption of cultured milk in the southern province of Zambia (Doctoral dissertation, The University of Zambia).
69. **Valdes, J.J. and Valdes, E.R. 2022.** Biological agents: threat and response. In *Handbook of Security Science*, pp. 739-769.
70. **Vanzini, V.R., Aguirre, N., Lugaresi, C.I., De Echaide, S.T., De Canavesio, V.G., Guglielmone, A.A. and Nielsen, K. 1998.** Evaluation of an indirect ELISA for the diagnosis of bovine brucellosis in milk and serum samples in dairy cattle in Argentina. *Preventive Veterinary Medicine*, **36**(3): 211-217.
71. **Verma, D. K. 2013.** Brucellosis in animals and human beings with special reference to Indian subcontinent. *International J. Integrative Sci. Innov. Tech*, **2**: 43-56.
72. **Wang, Y., Wang, Y., Peng, Q., Xiang, Z., Chen, Y., Wang, G. and Robertson, I. D. 2022.** A case study investigating the effects of emergency vaccination with *Brucella abortus* A19 vaccine on a dairy farm undergoing an abortion outbreak in China. *Animal Diseases*, **2**(1): 24.
73. **Wapenaar, W., Archer, S., Remnant, J. and Murphy, A. 2017.** Control of infectious diseases in dairy cattle. *Achieving Sustainable Production of Milk. Cambridge: Burleigh Dodd Science Publishing*, **45**: 7-486.
74. **Wright, P.F., Nilsson, E., Van Rooij, E.M., Lelenta, M. and Jeggo, M.H. 1993.** Standardisation and validation of enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay techniques for the detection of antibody in infectious disease diagnosis. *Revue Scientifique Et Technique (International Office of Epizootics)*, **12**(2): 435-450.
75. **Yousaf, A., Abbas, M., Laghari, R.A., Hassan, J., Rubab, F., Jamil, T. and Bibi, N. 2017.** Epidemiological investigation on outbreak of brucellosis at private dairy farms of Sindh, Pakistan. *Online J. Anim. Feed Res*, **7**(1): 09-12.